

PREDICTION OF EFFECTIVE STIFFNESS ON SHORT FIBER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Effective stiffness of short fiber composite with a three-dimensional random orientation of fibers is derived theoretically and compared with available experimental data. The laminate analogy and transformed laminate analogy are used for predictions of 2-D and 3-D random composites, respectively. The effective stiffness of random oriented fiber composite can be expressed in terms of longitudinal and transverse stiffnesses of unidirectional composites. The results of transformed laminate analogy is more accurate than other approaches such as Tsai-Pagano equation, Christensen-Waals equation, Cox equation, and Lavengood-Goettler equation, etc. Also the effective properties of random oriented fiber composite can be expressed in terms of fiber and matrix properties such as elastic modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Random oriented short fiber reinforced composites have become an attractive structural materials because of their high specific stiffness and strength, cheapness, and the capability of mass production. Unlike most conventional materials, mechanical properties of composites are highly anisotropic and show a nonlinear stress strain behavior, which results from the inhomogeneous composite structure and microcracking of constituents. To improve the design of structure and material efficiency, mechanical properties of composites have been studied extensively and predicted in various ways [5-27].

So far, only the laminate analogy model has been used for analyzing random oriented fiber composite. However, in this paper, the laminate analogy and the transformed laminate analogy are used to calculate mechanical properties of three dimensional random oriented (3-D) fiber composite, Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio. The laminate analogy is strongly dependent upon the assumption of physical volume average of engineering properties. Halpin and Pagano [14] have demonstrated that the short fiber composite system behaves like a 2-D random array of fiber which can be modeled by the laminate analogy. In order to get the model of 2-D composites, we need two assumptions. One is that a short fiber composite can be decomposed mathematically into layers of aligned short fibers and the other is that the laminate which is stacked at every angle, i.e., from 0° to 180° , is almost same as 2-D fiber composite, which is shown in Fig. (1). Thus, the properties of 2-D fiber composite can be determined through the classical laminate theory by averaging the properties of all laminate with different fiber orientations using the assumption of plane stress. To predict the engineering properties of 3-D fiber composite, the quasi-isotropic laminate (2-D laminate) is rotated along the 3 direction because the quasi-isotropic laminates on the 1-2 plane, which is shown in the Fig. (2). The stiffness of 2-D composite is calculated by integrating the stiffness of 2-D lamina with respect to the inclined angle from 3 axis, from 0° to 180° . Therefore, the average value of rotated quasi-isotropic laminate can be considered as those of 3-D fiber composite.

STIFFNESS PREDICTION BY THE LAMINATE ANALOGY

The random fiber composites of interest here are those laminate with fibers randomly oriented (2-D) in the laminate plane. Consider an orthotropic laminate with its principal material axes oriented at an angle with the reference coordinate axes. Using the transformation matrix, the relation between elements of $[Q]$, stiffness matrix, and $[Q']$, stiffness matrix referred to arbitrary axes, are obtained as follows [18, 19].

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q'_{11} &= Q_{11} \cos^4 \alpha + Q_{22} \sin^4 \alpha + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \alpha \cos^2 \alpha \\
 Q'_{22} &= Q_{22} \cos^4 \alpha + Q_{11} \sin^4 \alpha + 2(Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \alpha \cos^2 \alpha \\
 Q'_{12} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 4Q_{66}) \sin^2 \alpha \cos^2 \alpha + Q_{12}(\cos^4 \alpha + \sin^4 \alpha) \\
 Q'_{66} &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \sin^2 \alpha \cos^2 \alpha + Q_{66}(\sin^4 \alpha + \cos^4 \alpha) \\
 Q'_{16} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \cos^3 \alpha \sin \alpha - (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \cos \alpha \sin^3 \alpha \\
 Q'_{26} &= (Q_{11} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \cos \alpha \sin^3 \alpha - (Q_{22} - Q_{12} - 2Q_{66}) \cos^3 \alpha \sin \alpha
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

According to the laminate plate theory, the in-plane strains are uniform throughout the thickness under in-plane loadings. Since the random fiber composite is treated as a laminate with unidirectional plies in every direction, effective stiffness, \bar{Q}_{ij} is obtained by summing the plane stress moduli through the thickness in proportion to the percentage of the thickness of the k -th ply occupied of the n -ply laminate.

$$\bar{Q}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n Q'_{ij}{}^{(k)} a^{(k)} = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} Q'_{ij} d\alpha \tag{2}$$

where, $a^{(k)} = h^{(k)}/h$, $h^{(k)}$ is the ply thickness, and h is the thickness of laminate. Substituting Eqs.(1) into Eqs. (2) results in;

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{Q}_{11} &= \frac{1}{8} (3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}) = \bar{Q}_{22} \\
 \bar{Q}_{12} &= \frac{1}{8} (Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}) \\
 \bar{Q}_{16} &= \bar{Q}_{26} = 0 \\
 \bar{Q}_{66} &= \frac{1}{8} (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The engineering properties such as the elastic modulus, E_L , E_T , G_{LT} and Poisson's ratio, ν_{LT} can be expressed in terms of laminate stiffnesses as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_L &= (Q_{11} Q_{22} - Q_{12}^2) / Q_{22} \\
 \nu_{LT} &= Q_{12} / Q_{22} \\
 E_T &= (Q_{11} Q_{22} - Q_{12}^2) / Q_{11} \\
 G_{LT} &= Q_{66}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The overall engineering properties of the laminate with random oriented fibers in the laminate plane are obtained from the transformed laminate stiffness.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{E} &= (\bar{Q}_{11}^2 - \bar{Q}_{12}^2) / \bar{Q}_{11} = (\bar{Q}_{22}^2 - \bar{Q}_{12}^2) / \bar{Q}_{22} \\
 \bar{\nu} &= \bar{Q}_{12} / \bar{Q}_{22} = \bar{Q}_{12} / \bar{Q}_{11} \\
 \bar{G} &= \bar{Q}_{66}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (5) results in;

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \frac{Q_{11}^2 + Q_{22}^2 - 4Q_{12}^2 + 2Q_{11} Q_{22} + 8Q_{12} Q_{66} + 4Q_{11} Q_{66} + 4Q_{22} Q_{66}}{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}} \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}} \\ \bar{G} &= \frac{1}{8} (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

STIFFNESS PREDICTION BY THE TRANSFORMED LAMINATE ANALOGY

In order to express the engineering properties of 3-D composite in terms of stiffness matrices, we must rotate 2-D composite along the axis 3. Consider 2-D composite which is inclined by angle β toward axis 3 (or from the 1-2 plane). Using the transformation matrix, the relation between elements of $[\bar{Q}]$ and $[Q']$, stiffness matrix referred to arbitrary axes in 3-D case, is obtained and has the same form as Eq (1). By rotating 2-D composite along the axis 3 from 0° to 180° , the effective stiffness of 3-D composite, \bar{Q}_{ij} , also can be expressed in terms of $[Q']$.

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{Q}'_{11} &= \frac{1}{8} (3\bar{Q}_{11} + 3\bar{Q}_{22} + 2\bar{Q}_{12} + 4\bar{Q}_{66}) = \bar{Q}'_{33} \\ \bar{Q}'_{13} &= \frac{1}{8} (\bar{Q}_{11} + \bar{Q}_{22} + 6\bar{Q}_{12} - 4\bar{Q}_{66}) \\ \bar{Q}'_{15} &= \bar{Q}'_{35} = 0 \\ \bar{Q}'_{55} &= \frac{1}{8} (\bar{Q}_{11} + \bar{Q}_{22} - 2\bar{Q}_{12} + 4\bar{Q}_{66})\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

The overall engineering properties of 3-D composite is almost the same style as that of Eq. (5);

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \bar{Q}'_{11} - \frac{2\bar{Q}'_{13}{}^2}{\bar{Q}'_{11} + \bar{Q}'_{13}} \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{\bar{Q}'_{13}}{\bar{Q}'_{11} + \bar{Q}'_{13}} \\ \bar{G} &= \bar{Q}'_{55}\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

In order to express the engineering properties in terms of the $[Q]$ matrix, substitute Eq. (3) and (7) into Eq. (8), the results are:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \frac{1}{16} \left[6Q_{11} + 6Q_{22} + 4Q_{12} + 8Q_{66} - \frac{(Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})^2}{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 2Q_{12}} \right] \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{4Q_{11} + 4Q_{22} + 8Q_{12}} \\ \bar{G} &= \frac{1}{8} (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Thus engineering properties of 3-D composite can be predicted by original [Q] matrix. Comparing of Eq. (6) to Eq. (9) shows that engineering properties of 2-D composite are higher than those of 3-D case.

DISCUSSION

Eqs. (9) are the final results of 3-D composite. These expressions can be used to predict the mechanical properties of various combinations of fibers and matrices. Using the Halpin -Tsai equation, engineering properties of orthotropic ply can be expressed in terms of those of fiber and matrix. Also stiffness matrix can be derived in terms of engineering properties of lamina. Eq. (6) for 2-D composite can be changed as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \frac{1}{8\{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}} \left[\frac{3E_L + 3E_T + 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L)\nu_{LT}^2\}}{3E_L + 3E_T + 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}} \left[\frac{E_L + E_T + 6\nu_{LT}E_T - 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{3E_L + 3E_T + 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}} \right]^2 \right] \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{E_L + E_T + 6\nu_{LT}E_T - 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{3E_L + 3E_T + 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}} \\ \bar{G} &= \frac{E_L + E_T - 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{8 \{1 - (E_T / E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

And for 3-D composite,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{E} &= \frac{1}{8\{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}} \left[\frac{3E_L + 3E_T + 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L)\nu_{LT}^2\}}{2E_L + 2E_T + 4\nu_{LT}E_T} \left[\frac{E_L + E_T + 6\nu_{LT}E_T - 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{2E_L + 2E_T + 4\nu_{LT}E_T} \right]^2 \right] \\ \bar{\nu} &= \frac{E_L + E_T + 6\nu_{LT}E_T - 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{4E_L + 4E_T + 8\nu_{LT}E_T} \\ \bar{G} &= \frac{E_L + E_T - 2\nu_{LT}E_T + 4G_{LT} \{1 - (E_T/E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}{8 \{1 - (E_T / E_L) \nu_{LT}^2\}}\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

Eqs (11) can be simplified using Tsai and Pagano's approach [20];

$$\bar{E} = \frac{1}{8} \left[3E_L + 5E_T - \frac{(E_L + E_T)^2}{2E_L + 3E_T} \right]$$

$$\bar{\nu} = \frac{E_L + E_T}{4E_L + 6E_T} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{G} = \frac{1}{8} (E_L + 2E_T)$$

Various equations which predict the effective stiffness of random fiber composites are tabulated in Table 1. The necessary system data are displayed in Table 2. Theoretical values are compared to experimental data. Fig. 3 represents the dependence of effective stiffness on volume fraction of fibers in 2-D composite and Fig. 4 represents that for 3-D case. It is shown that the predictions of Tsai-Pagano and Christensen-Waals show good correlation to experimental data, but present analysis from the laminate analogy is the most accurate than any other prediction. For 3-D composite, Lavengood-Goettler's assumption [7] is used, which states that the mechanical properties of 3-D composite are about 20% lower than those of 2-D composite. The results of this study predicts these data reasonably well, which is shown in Fig. 4.

The effect of fiber aspect ratio on effective stiffness of 2-D and 3-D boron/epoxy composites is shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. Young's modulus of boron and epoxy are 60×10^6 psi and 0.5×10^6 psi, shear moduli of boron and epoxy are 25×10^6 psi and 0.2×10^6 psi, and Poisson's ratios of boron and epoxy are 0.2 and 0.4, respectively. It is shown that experimental [24] and theoretical data match very well at low aspect ratio and these do not match well as the aspect ratio increases. This might be due to the interaction between fibers, fiber orientation and Poisson's ratio effect. It is reasonable to neglect the interactions between the fibers at low aspect ratio. However, the possibility of interaction between fibers increases as aspect ratio increases. Also it becomes more difficult to control the orientation of fibers at the higher aspect ratio case. Poisson's ratio becomes less adequate, as the aspect ratio increases, due to the possible interaction between fibers, and alignments of fibers. Although exact contributions of each factor are not known, combinations of these affect the final results of this theoretical approach. It might be necessary to study further in this aspect to understand the mechanical behavior of short fiber composites.

CONCLUSIONS

It is demonstrated in this study that the stiffness of 3-D random oriented composite can be analyzed using transformed laminate analogy. From this study, following comments are made;

1. In random oriented fiber composite, the stiffness of 2-D composite is higher than that of 3-D one.
2. The transformed laminate analogy gives more accurate results of effective stiffness of 3-D composite than other proposed relations.
3. The effective stiffness of 3-D composite can be expressed in terms of mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix.
4. In order to predict effective stiffness more precisely, poisson's ratio relation and fiber interaction should be included.

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Table 1. materials properties

Polycarbonate	1/8 in. E-glass fiber
$E_m = 3.16 \times 10^5$ psi	$E_f = 12 \times 10^6$ psi
$G_m = 1.5 \times 10^5$ psi	$G_f = 4 \times 10^6$ psi
$\nu_m = 0.35$	$\nu_f = 0.22$
	Aspect ratio 313

Table 2. Equations which predict the effective stiffness

	2 - D	3 - D
Cox	$E=V_f E_f/3, G=V_f E_f/8$	$E=V_f E_f/6, G=V_f E_f/15$
Modified Cox	$E=E_L/3, G=E_L/8$	$E=E_L/6, G=E_L/15$
Christensen Waals*	$E=V_f E_f/3 + (1+V_f)E_m$	$E=[1+(1+\nu_m)V_f]E_m + E_f V_f/6$
Tsai-Pagano	$E=(3E_L + 5E_T)/8$ $G=(E_L + 2E_T)/8$	-
Lavengood-Goettler	-	$E=(E_L + 4E_T)/5$

Fig.1 Laminate analogy model [10]

Fig.2 Transformed laminate analogy model

Fig. 3 Dependence of the effective stiffness on volume fraction of 2 - D case [15].

Fig. 4 Dependence of the effective stiffness on volume fraction of 3 - D case [15].

Fig. 5 Effect of aspect ratio on the effective stiffness of 2 - D case in boron/epoxy system [16].

Fig. 6 Effect of aspect ratio on the effective stiffness of 2 - D case in boron/epoxy system [16].